

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-160-IBN-5-2% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	16	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 160
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/4/2023 11:36:04 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 8:57:07 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.218	7876547	50.34	619083
2	8.991	7771575	49.66	546138

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-129-IBN-5-2%	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	54	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 129
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/6/2023 4:47:54 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 8:56:14 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.966	385186	1.87	32248
2	8.573	20176287	98.13	1548736